

Biochemical Methane Potential of Recirculating Aquaculture System Sludge Under Different Salinity Conditions and Biochar Effects

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Abstract

In this study, the biochemical methane potential (BMP) of recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) sludge in freshwater, brackish, and seawater conditions was determined, with and without biochar. Freshwater conditions yielded the highest biogas ($804 \pm 16 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{gVS}^{-1}$), followed by brackish ($744 \pm 3 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{gVS}^{-1}$) and seawater ($571 \pm 13 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{gVS}^{-1}$). Adding biochar increased biogas yields by 6%, 4%, and 10% under freshwater, brackish, and seawater conditions, respectively. CH_4 content was between 63.2–65.8% in all conditions, but it required longer time in seawater (12.9 days) to reach over 63% while it took 7.2 days in both freshwater and brackish water. These findings underscore biochar's potential to enhance anaerobic digestion across varying salinity levels.

Keywords

Anaerobic digestion; aquaculture sludge; biochemical methane potential; biochar; BMP; salinity

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture industry is one of the fastest-growing food production sectors globally and it has an important role in providing livelihoods and economic opportunities, especially in coastal regions. In 2022, the worldwide aquatic animal production was 185 million tonnes, of which 51% (94 million tonnes) is produced by aquaculture industry, while 49% (91 million tonnes) was from capture fisheries (FAO, 2024). However, the rapid expansion of aquaculture has raised concerns regarding the environmental impacts, particularly related to water quality degradation and the management of waste produced during farming operations, due to the high content of suspended solids, nitrogen, phosphorus, and various organic matters (Munguti et al., 2020). Currently, Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) have been used as a technology for intensive land-based fish farming. RAS enable high waste removal efficiency and recycling of water up to 99%. However, RAS is energy-intensive, requiring 15–30 kWh·kg⁻¹ of fish (Kashem et al., 2023), primarily for oxygen supply and water circulation. To improve RAS sustainability, resource recovery offers a promising approach.

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a proven method for energy recovery from biomass. AD is an approach to effectively treat sludge from RAS. AD contributes to reduces the dry matter volume of sludge waste, to recover biogas, to reduce carbon footprint and the cost of sludge stabilization and disposal (da Borso et al., 2021). However, applying AD to saline fish sludge presents significant challenges. High sodium concentrations ($> 10 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) are known to inhibit AD processes (Gebauer, 2004). Furthermore, elevated sulfate levels, which are reduced to sulfide under anaerobic conditions, and the ammonia generated from the degradation of proteins, can act as additional limiting factors for the effective treatment of aquaculture effluents through AD (da Borso et al., 2021). Biochar can eliminate inhibitory effects of salt, ammonia and volatile fatty acids by adsorption, increasing the buffer capacity, and increasing the electron transfer between microbial communities (Manga et al., 2023).

The overall objective for this biochemical methane potential (BMP) study was to investigate the

methane potential and biodegradability of RAS sludge (smolt farm sludge) under different salinity conditions and the effect of biochar on methane production. Moreover, the study aimed to investigate how the microbial dynamics were changed through the BMP test.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Substrate and inoculum

The substrate used for the BMP assessment in this study consisted of sludge collected from a land-based fish (salmon – smolt) aquaculture farm operated by SalMar Farming AS in Tjuin, Norway. The concentrated fish sludge was obtained following the drum filter separation process in the RAS.

The inoculum was sourced from the digestate of three identical lab-scale semi-continuously stirred tank reactors (CSTRs) operated under mesophilic (36°C – 39°C) conditions. The CSTRs operated as anaerobic digesters treating the same RAS sludge used as the substrate in the BMP study.

The main characteristics of the inoculum were as follows: total solids (TS) $35.3 \pm 0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, volatile solids (VS) $22.2 \pm 0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, total COD (tCOD) $30.5 \pm 0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, total ammonium nitrogen (TAN) $1.3 \pm 0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, volatile fatty acid/alkalinity (FOS/TAC) 0.22, and pH 8.3. The RAS sludge had the following characteristics: TS $99.4 \pm 0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, VS $78.3 \pm 0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, tCOD $129.2 \pm 6.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, TAN $1.7 \pm 0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, FOS/TAC 13.6, salinity 0%, and pH 5.4. Before the beginning of the BMP test, the inoculum was continuously mixed and pre-incubated for one week at mesophilic temperatures to remove residual biogas and deplete any remaining readily biodegradable organic material.

Experimental set-up and BMP test

The BMP test was performed in 45 sealed glass bottles (300 mL working volume) over 50 days under three salinity conditions: freshwater (0%), brackish water (1.2%), and seawater (3.3%) at 39 °C (Figure 1). Each salinity condition had three negative controls ($2 \text{ g VS}_{\text{inoculum}}\cdot\text{bottle}^{-1}$), positive controls ($2 \text{ g VS}_{\text{inoculum}}\cdot\text{bottle}^{-1} + 1 \text{ g Cellulose}\cdot\text{bottle}^{-1}$), and experimental including substrate ($2 \text{ g VS}_{\text{inoculum}}\cdot\text{bottle}^{-1} + 1 \text{ g VS}_{\text{RAS sludge}}\cdot\text{bottle}^{-1}$) tested in triplicates for reproducibility and statistical analysis. Additional tests evaluated biochar effects on RAS sludge under the same salinity conditions with same setup. Biochar tests included $0.8 \text{ g biochar}\cdot\text{g VS}_{\text{RAS sludge}}^{-1}$. Salinity conditions were adjusted with $11.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and $33.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of synthetic sea salt (Aquarium Systems Instant Ocean) for brackish and seawater bottles, respectively.

Figure 1. Figuration of BMP test set-up

The biochar used in this study was produced from anaerobic digestate sourced from the before mentioned CSTRs. The digestate was centrifuged, dried at 60 °C, crushed, and pyrolyzed at 600 °C for 60 minutes under a nitrogen gas flow ($5 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$). The resulting biochar was washed, sieved to

particle sizes >2 mm, and dried at 60 °C. The biochar had a pH of 10.6, conductivity of 7.05 mS·cm⁻¹, and underwent no pre- or post-modification treatments.

The headspace pressure of the BMP test bottles was measured at specific intervals to monitor biogas production. The biogas composition, including methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and H₂S, was analyzed using micro gas chromatography (Agilent 990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Net cumulative biogas yield of RAS sludge (smolt sludge) under each condition was calculated by removing the negative control group results from the substrate group (Figure 2). Biogas content of the substrate group bottles is presented in Figure 3.

Under freshwater (0% salinity) conditions, the net cumulative biogas yield of RAS sludge after 50 days was 804 ± 16 mL·gVS⁻¹, with biogas composition of 64.2 ± 0.1% CH₄, 33.9 ± 0.3% CO₂, 0.2 ± 0% H₂S, and 1.7 ± 0% other gases. For brackish water (1.2% salinity), the yield was 744 ± 3 mL·gVS⁻¹, containing 65.6 ± 0.1% CH₄, 32.6 ± 0.3% CO₂, 1.6 ± 0% H₂S, and 0.2 ± 0% other gases. Under seawater (3.3% salinity), the yield dropped to 571 ± 13 mL·gVS⁻¹, with 65.8 ± 0.2% CH₄, 27 ± 0.2% CO₂, 4.2 ± 0.1% H₂S, and 3 ± 0% other gases. The results indicate that RAS sludge generates 8% and 41% more biogas under freshwater conditions compared to brackish and seawater conditions, respectively. While the CH₄ content of biogas was similar under brackish and seawater conditions, it was 1.5% lower in freshwater. Achieving over 60% CH₄ in biogas requires 7.2 days under freshwater and brackish water conditions but extends to 12.9 days under seawater conditions. Notably, significant H₂S production (4.2%) was observed under seawater conditions (Figure 3), likely due to the sulfur content in seawater. In previous studies, Suhr et al. (2015), reported a BMP of 318 ± 29 mL CH₄·g VS⁻¹ for freshwater RAS sludge, while Choudhury et al. (2023), documented 519 mL CH₄·g⁻¹ VS with 70% methane for freshwater aquaculture wastewater. Gebauer (2004), observed AD inhibition under high salinity but achieved 0.26–0.28 L CH₄·g VS⁻¹ after diluting the feedstock 1:1 with tap water. da Borso et al. (2021), demonstrated that higher inoculum-to-sludge ratios produced the highest BMP (564.2 NmL CH₄·g VS⁻¹) under brackish conditions.

Figure 2. BMP test results of RAS sludge under different salinity and biochar additive conditions (A) cumulative biogas yield profile throughout the test (B) BMP values in the end of the study

In freshwater with biochar, the net cumulative biogas yield was 855 ± 19 mL·gVS⁻¹, with 63.2 ± 0.2% CH₄, 35.3 ± 0.2% CO₂, 1.5 ± 0% H₂S, and 0 ± 0% other gases. In brackish water with biochar, the yield was 775 ± 19 mL·gVS⁻¹, with 65.1 ± 0.1% CH₄, 33.1 ± 0% CO₂, 1.5 ± 0.1% H₂S, and 0.3 ± 0% other gases. Under seawater conditions with biochar, the yield was 629 ± 39 mL·gVS⁻¹, with 65.7 ± 0.2% CH₄, 26.9 ± 0.2% CO₂, 4.0 ± 0.1% H₂S, and 3.4 ± 0% other gases. The results show that adding biochar to RAS sludge increases biogas production by 6%, 4%, and 10% under freshwater, brackish

water, and seawater conditions, respectively, compared to conditions without biochar. It is reported in previous studies that biochar had 16–25% improvement in CH₄ production rate (Manga et al., 2023). The CH₄ content of biogas is slightly lower (by 1%) under freshwater and brackish water conditions with biochar but remains unchanged under seawater conditions. Similar to non-biochar conditions, reaching over 60% CH₄ in biogas requires 7.2 days in freshwater and brackish water and 12.9 days in seawater. Significant H₂S production (4%) was also observed under seawater with biochar conditions (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Distribution of CH₄, CO₂, H₂S and other gases in produced biogas under different salinity and biochar additive conditions

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